

Valorization of dried nuts with hard skin

Introduction

The OG had as Objective the valorization of dried nuts, diversifying their use. For the almonds and hazelnuts, to contribute to their long lasting, presentation, and conservation, making possible to attain distant markets. Almonds: to explore the potential of ground, flour, granulated and laminated. Also explore its processed value: fried, in jams, toasted, with meat or in liqueurs or other drinks. ground, flour, granulated and laminated. also explore its processed value: fried, in jams, toasted, with meat or in liqueurs. For the by-products such as the bark, explore their use as fertilizer, use in animal feed, as a source of bioactive compounds or as gum. For each of these objectives, tests and essays were made, according to the variability of the fruit, the time consuming, the cost and the real transport conditions. The humidity, microbial content, storage temperature in the different stages of product preparation were particularly sensitive aspects.

Hazelnuts: The intention was to potentiate this crop in Portugal by diversifying its use and presentation (indirectly the price) and achieving export. The physical-chemical characterization of the different varieties was carried out and good practices were established. For post-harvest, attention was paid to peeling, packaging and transportation, with special relevance for tropical countries.

Connection with the Project Valor+ (<https://valormais.cncfs.pt/>): The 'ValorMais' project aimed to promote the valorization of by-products from agricultural, agri-food and forestry sector through its characterization and quantification. In this sense, the OG co-promote the use and valorization of the so called "waste" (by-products) in a view of circular economy. The forest waste of other varieties such as eucalyptus, pine and quercus are also considered here in Valor+, building a platform to inform about the stock, use and commercial operators in this field.

Lessons learned

Several scientific articles were published, as a way to promote the results and the international discussion on these subjects. The cooperation between research institutions was productive, as in other OG. The essays are expected to go further, as well the efforts to achieve the effective advantages for producers. The foreign competition is an aspect to be studied, yet. The enlargement of the cooperation with other partners, beyond

the promoters of this OG, was an added value to better disseminate and promote the use of the all the products valences.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://valnuts.cncfs.pt/projeto>

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